

STUDY OF IMMUNOLOGICAL REACTIVITY, REPRODUCTIVE FUNCTION AND HEALTH OF ATHLETES

Khaknazarov Kurbon Kushayevich

Senior Lecturer, Faculty of Sports Activities and Management
Termez State University

Annotation: The article discusses the most important issues and features of the immunology of sports, notes the relationship between the decrease in immunological reactivity and the morbidity of athletes in modern sports, and the immunological aspects of the occurrence and violation of their reproductive function.

Key words: immunological reactivity, T- and B-immune systems, lymphocytes, immunology of reproduction, autoantibodies.

Introduction. Currently, millions of people are involved in physical education and sports [2]. Such activities significantly reduce the incidence of illness, increase life expectancy and the body's resistance to various types of unfavorable environmental factors. However, modern elite sport is sometimes associated with loads on the edge of a person's physiological capabilities [1, 4, 7]. Under these conditions, improper organization of the training process, its insufficient individualization, a combination of sports training with intensive work or study in the presence of even compensated defects in health can lead to the occurrence of pathological conditions [3, 5, 6].

The problems of sports immunology are very relevant today and are of interest not only to the sports doctor, but also to the coach. And this is quite understandable, since the trend towards an increase in the number of diseases among athletes continues, which, in turn, makes it necessary not only to study the effect of muscle

load, especially of a limiting nature, but also to apply immunological methods in the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of diseases.

Sports immunology, like modern immunology, is a relatively young science among other medical and biological disciplines. Originating as an applied science, sports immunology has evolved as a new therapeutic approach to the prevention of infectious diseases among sports participants. Unfortunately, the number of diseases in athletes is quite high, as evidenced by the data of some researchers [9, 10, 11, 13]. It is during the period when athletes are at the highest stage of the adaptation process - in a state of training - that incredible ease of illness is observed [8].

According to researchers, a paradoxical situation can be traced: on the one hand, the functional capabilities of the body increase, as evidenced by good, stable performance (increased athletic performance), on the other hand, the immunological reactivity of the body decreases. For example, the leading indicator of phagocytosis, the Wright index (the average number of microbes captured by one segmented neutrophil) can be less than 1.0 (normally it is usually above 3.0, sometimes reaching 8 units. Suppression of immunity is visible not only in the cellular link, but also in the humoral one, up to the appearance of immunodeficiency phenomena [12, 14, 15].

Researchers believe that the positive effect of extreme muscle loads manifests itself, as a rule, only against the background of sufficient functional readiness of the athlete's body. Otherwise, hard work provokes a state of deep fatigue; the athlete simply does not have time to recover in the periods between training or competitions [16, 18].

In this regard, athletes of team sports (football, hockey), especially those teams that claim to qualify for the final part of the competition, find themselves in difficult conditions. A large number of meetings during the year and their emotional intensity contribute (provoke) the development of states of overstrain and overtraining [17].

Emotional stress is characterized by a decrease in correlations between individual indicators of functional systems. This indicates disintegration under stress of multi-level interaction of indicators of functional systems of homeostasis [19, 20]. Particular care should be taken in the desire of the coach, and sometimes the athlete, to include in classes and do large volumes of training work in the preparatory period, when the level of functional readiness is not yet high enough; at moments when the athlete does not have time to recover due to a busy competition schedule, in a situation where the athlete performs muscle work against the background of a latent infection or after an illness suffered in the recent past (7-10 days). In these cases, we can talk about the pathogenic role of inadequate muscle load.

This combination of body conditions and muscle load leads to readaptation. Disruption of the functioning and interconnection of not only supporting systems (cardiovascular, respiratory, blood systems), but also almost all parts of the immune system. In this situation, competitive and training muscle work act as a risk factor that has a negative effect on the immune system.

Modern sports are characterized by very high physical and emotional stress. Sports achievements and records become a source of pride not only for the athlete himself, but also for millions of fans. At the same time, the responsibility of not only the athlete, but also the coach increases. This often leads to acceleration of training, forcing highly qualified athletes to participate in competitions with health problems. "Epidemics" of colds during important competitions most directly affect sports results. A kind of vicious chain arises: intense loads exceeding the physiological capabilities of the athlete in order to achieve maximum results, impaired immunological reactivity, illness, decreased performance. At the same time, immunological changes can be one of the earliest signs indicating the possibility of health problems, the occurrence of so-called premorbid, pre-morbid conditions.

Existing ideas about the high sensitivity of immune reactions to the overloads of modern sports are valid, first of all, for indicators of the T-system of immunity. During immunological examination of athletes, one or another degree of decrease in

the number of T-lymphocytes in the blood and inhibition of their functional properties in the reaction of blast transformation of lymphocytes with T-mitogens and phytohemagglutinin are observed. These changes often precede the onset of certain diseases in athletes. Moreover, these diseases are found in athletes with signs of insufficient function of the T-immune system.

Some authors, based on studying and assessing the state of the B-immune system, come to the conclusion that it is possible for athletes to develop changes characteristic of secondary immunodeficiencies. However, the inhibition of B-system indicators is less significant compared to indicators characterizing the state of the T-system (no changes in the number of B-lymphocytes in the blood). Even so, during periods of extreme stress and under the influence of fatigue, the content of immunoglobulins in the blood may decrease.

The production of autoantibodies, which requires a violation of immunological tolerance for its implementation, is also associated with the functional activity of B lymphocytes. There are few indications in the literature that moderate physical activity helps to reduce the content of autoantibodies, which, apparently, help neutralize toxic metabolic products, which are more intense in athletes. However, it is necessary to further study the possibility of auto-aggressive action of autoantibodies when they are formed in significant concentrations and fixed to appropriate tissue substrates. The authors reveal increased concentrations of both complement-fixing antitissue autoantibodies and precipitins, as well as circulating immune complexes, in athletes.

The study of reproductive function in athletes and the significance of immunological changes for this function is currently receiving increasing attention. Research is carried out in various directions: immunology of fertilization, immunology of intrauterine development, immunology of the postnatal period. As noted in studies, cases where it is not possible to establish the cause of infertile marriages are not uncommon. Immunological studies and determination of humoral antibodies to sperm make it possible to establish the immunological nature of

infertility in 15-20% of infertile marriages of unknown etiology. The use of a cytotoxic test and the reaction of inhibition of leukocyte migration can significantly increase this percentage to 48-75%.

Freund showed the participation of immunological factors in the damage to the testis. Immunization of guinea pigs with a homologous testis homogenate with the so-called Freund's stimulator (an immunogenesis stimulator consisting of oils and tuberculosis bacteria) led not only to the intensive formation of anti-testis antibodies, but also to severe damage to the testis of immunized animals. Autoimmune aspermatogenesis developed.

Conclusions. Thus, the introduction of immunological research methods into the practice of sports medicine will help optimize the training process, achieve high sports results while improving the health of athletes. The presence of immunological disorders requires the closest attention of a sports doctor, consultation with an immunologist to decide on the possibility and advisability of continuing training and sports.

At present, there is no reason to assert that reproductive dysfunction in athletes, including highly qualified athletes, is associated with intense training loads. However, the materials available in the literature justify the need to conduct clinical and immunological studies in the direction of “immunology of reproduction of athletes,” since immunological factors are very significant for the reproductive function.

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